

THE PROCESS OF IMPLEMENTING PUBLIC POLICY IN VIETNAM: RESEARCH POLICY ON TRAINING AND FOSTERING KHMER CIVIL SERVANTS IN THE MEKONG DELTA

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Abstract

The public policy implementation process plays a vital role in implementing and effectively implementing public policies in Vietnam- a method to systematize theory and analyze data from 875 surveyed samples. The policy implementation process for training and retraining civil servants follows a seven-step process, including (1) building a policy implementation plan; (2) disseminating and propagating policy implementation contents; (3) assigning and coordinating policy implementation; (4) maintaining policy implementation; (5) adjust policy implementation; (6) monitor, inspect, and urge policy implementation; (7) summarize, evaluate, and learn from policy implementation. Research results provide information and evaluate the implementation of training and fostering policies. Develop a process to implement policies on training Khmer civil servants in the Mekong Delta region. Studying this model will help implement training and retraining policies; civil servants achieve higher efficiency, reduce costs and improve quality. Besides, it increases understanding of the culture, religion, customs and practices of the Khmer people. From the research results, several awards have been given to improve the effectiveness of the policy implementation of training and retraining of civil servants in Vietnam.

Keywords: Process, public policy, training, civil servants, Vietnam, Mekong Delta.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ethnic minority civil servants played an essential role in the Vietnamese revolution. Training, fostering, and fostering ethnic minority civil servants has been conducted regularly, carefully, scientifically, rigorously, and effectively by the state (Bland et al., 2021). The quality of ethnic minority civil servants has been improved, operating more effectively, contributing significantly to consolidating and developing the excellent unity bloc of ethnic groups, and promoting economic and social development and stability politics.

Implementing policy on training and retraining of civil servants is the process of putting this policy into practice through the issuance of documents, plans and programs to implement the policy. Implementing training and fostering policies for civil servants is an organized activity.

It aims to mobilize all resources, including human, financial, and physical facilities and implementation organizations, to realize the policy objectives (Alemán et al., 2018). Implementing the policy of training and fostering Khmer civil servants in the Mekong Delta region is the entire process of mobilizing and arranging resources to implement the policy (Badri & Al Mansoori, 2015).

Policy implementation should follow a strict and unified procedure in order to achieve the goal of policy implementation training and retraining Khmer civil servants in the Mekong Delta. Implement the policy of training and retraining Khmer civil servants in the Northern Delta to affirm the correctness of the policy (Besfat, 2022). This is the process of putting policies into practice with a specific target audience of Khmer civil servants to improve the quality of civil servants to meet public service requirements in the new situation (Hai et al., 2023).

Clarifying the process of implementing policy on training and retraining Khmer civil servants in the Northern Delta, contributing to supplementing the theoretical basis on implementing the policy on training and retraining civil servants; Evaluating the implementation of policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants.

2. RESEARCH METHODS

The method of classification and systematization of the theory. This method aims to conduct the selection and variety of documents according to research needs. From there, build a theoretical framework suitable for research purposes and requirements. Besides, synthesis methods, analysis and statistics are used to analyze the implementation of policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants and the results after implementing the procedures.

At the same time, set up tables and charts to reinforce the reliability and quickly reflect the research status. Sociological investigation methods. The author selects districts and districts with many Khmer people living in the Mekong Delta for the survey. We collected data using random sampling with 875 survey questionnaires from Khmer civil servants.

Likert scale is used to evaluate the level of acceptance, with five groups including (1) not good, (2) less good, (3) average, (4) reasonable, (5) very good. The survey results will be an essential source of information to gain a practical overview of policy implementation results, relationships between subjects participating in policy implementation, and the role of local authorities. Methods in finding resources, propagandizing and advocating, evaluating and maintaining the results of implementing policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS

3.1. Develop plans to implement training and fostering policies for civil servants

The State issues policies and general regulations nationwide. Each ministry, branch and locality is responsible for implementing them. Depending on the actual situation in ministries, departments and localities, there are appropriate ways to implement it as long as the goals do not change (Beuermann & Amelina, 2018). Therefore, each church, branch and locality must

develop a specific plan to implement proper training and fostering policies for ethnic minority civil servants. The goal for training and promoting civil servants of ethnic minorities is the concretization of the State's policy of training and fostering civil servants appropriate to the time and characteristics of the specific situation of each locality, agency, and unit. Training and promoting plans for civil servants are often built for a certain period, such as long-term plans (5 years, ten years, 20 years), medium-term plans (2-3 years), and short-term goals. Developing training and retraining plans for ethnic minority civil servants is an essential and decisive content in the training and retraining of civil servants (Bostanci & Erdem, 2020).

Planning is designing for a desired future and an effective way to do it. It is a sketch of how resources, time, and effort are used to achieve what is expected. Planning is investigating, researching, anticipating what will happen and focusing all measures to reach a reasonable goal (Khong et al., 2023). It is deciding what each organization, agency or individual has to do, how to do it, and where and when to complete it. Based on Decree No. 18/2010/ND-CP dated March 5, 2010, of the Government; Decree No. 101/2017/ND-CP dated September 1, 2017, of the Government; Decision No. 163/QD-TTg dated January 25, 2016, of the Prime Minister approving the Scheme on training and retraining of civil servants and public employees for the period 2016 - 2025. Decision No. 402/QD-TTg dated March 14 2016, of the Prime Minister approved the Project "Development of the contingent of civil servants and public employees of ethnic minorities in the new period".

Decision No. 162/QD-UBDT dated March 26, 2018, Approving the Plan to develop the Project "Preferential Policies for socio-economic Development for Khmer ethnic minority areas; Training and fostering the Khmer ethnic minorities in the Mekong Delta" issued by the Committee for Ethnic Minorities. The decrees and decisions issued by the Government and the Committee for Ethnic Minority Affairs are the legal basis and favourable conditions for the provinces in the central region to give plans to implement policies on training and retraining of civil servants Khmer people in the Mekong Delta region (Hai & Ngan, 2022).

Thus, each locality has developed a program suitable to its socio-economic conditions based on absorbing and studying the central government's policies. Survey results for developing training and retraining policy implementation plans show that creating a plan to implement training and retraining policies for Khmer civil servants' planning is not scientific or reasonable (Denhardt & Denhardt, 2015). There is no specific plan for Khmer civil servants; coordination tasks must be more precise, leading to collective responsibility, and individuals are not high in policy implementation.

Figure 1: Evaluation of Khmer civil servants on the effectiveness of developing training and retraining policy implementation plans

Source: Summary of survey data processing results, September 2023

Thus, there are still difficulties in localities that still need to issue separate plans for training and fostering Khmer civil servants, which makes it difficult for advisory work to implement the plan. Therefore, in the coming time, the localities in the Mekong Delta will continue to adjust and supplement the program to complete and disseminate it to the Khmer people's level and civil servants to implement the training and fostering plan with results. At the same time, the provinces continue to develop their strategies for training and cultivating Khmer civil servants.

3.2. Disseminate and propagate contents of policy implementation on training and retraining of civil servants

The local governments of the provinces in the central region make plans to implement the policy of training and retraining. Khmer civil servants focus on disseminating and propagating policies to put the policy into practice for agencies, units, and civil servants (Gaurav & Ram, 2020). To communicate and propagate policy implementation, the People's Committee of the provinces directs the organizing committee and the Department of Home Affairs to preside over. Coordinate with branches, departments and districts to organize information, disseminate and propagate according to the policy, and follow up with specific tasks to implement the policy.

The form of dissemination and propaganda is carried out by the government through propaganda on television stations, posting on the electronic portal system of districts, departments and branches, and at the same time being propagated on banners and billboards (Lapuente & Van de Walle, 2020). Through the conference, disseminate, reproduce and deploy to civil servants. In addition, the local government also assigns socio-political organizations to organize meetings to implement policies.

According to the survey results, the famous and essential propaganda content meets the needs, demonstrating comprehensiveness with complete information about the policy. The forms of propaganda are also quite diverse and suitable for each audience (Gregg, 2015). In general, disseminating, propagandizing and implementing procedures on training and fostering Khmer civil servants meets the content and form requirements in planned coordination. However, implementing propaganda to implement the policy still has some things that could be improved, such as the form of propaganda in some places being superficial and unsuitable for each beneficiary group. The coordination of propaganda work of agencies is sometimes not tight and irregular. Therefore, some civil servants need to clearly understand the essential contents of the policy, especially the training and retraining allowance regime, training and retraining subjects according to each program, affecting the effectiveness of the implementation policy.

3.3. Assign and coordinate the implementation of training and fostering policies for civil servants

Implementing policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants is organized according to state policies and implementation plans of provinces in the Mekong Delta region. The assignment and coordination of implementation of training and fostering policies for Khmer civil servants is carried out. The Department of Home Affairs coordinates with the organizing committee to advise the People's Committee of the provinces in the region to develop a plan. Based on the goals of the provincial and district people's committees, departments and branches deploy and develop strategies to implement policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants in the communities. With the tasks assigned by the People's Committee, the district internal affairs departments regularly advise the People's Committee to develop plans to implement this policy. At the same time, continuously monitor, check, urge, and compile a list of qualified civil servants to report to the competent authority to send them for training and retraining. Assigning direct monitoring of training and fostering work for civil servants (Lakovic, 2021). The government is responsible for selecting the proper subjects for training and retraining and promptly reporting the results of sending civil servants for training and retraining to the provincial organizing committee and the Department of Home Affairs. Coordinate closely to inspect, supervise and monitor the learning of civil servants, resolve arising problems, and find resources to support civil servants in training and retraining nourishment (Le et al., 2022).

3.4. Maintain the implementation of policies on training, retraining and civil servants

Based on training and retraining plans, Khmer civil servants in the period or annually. The provinces in the Mekong Delta region conduct statistics, evaluate implementation results and set tasks to maintain the implementation of training and retraining of civil servants for the following year (Miyeon et al., 2021). Since then, the provinces' agencies, units, departments, and branches have disseminated and propagated policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants and encouraging them to study and improve their qualifications (Liu et al., 2020). After implementing the policy of training and fostering Khmer civil servants in the Mekong Delta, the quality of Khmer civil servants in the districts has been improved, performing tasks effectively promoting economic development - society in the locality (Mai et al., 2016).

According to assigned tasks, the Department of Internal Affairs has researched, surveyed, and proposed solutions to implement training and fostering policies for civil servants and proposed improvements to policies for civil servants students submit to the province for the central government to consider (Moteki, 2022). The region and central government have made adjustments, supplements and improvements to policies to suit practical social conditions, helping policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants to be maintained and stabilized and determine and promote long-term effects in life. In addition, the districts have reviewed the allocation of policy implementation resources to ensure that policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants are maintained, organized and implemented effectively and to ensure transparency in the time frame set out by the policy implementation plan. In general, policy maintenance is paid attention to and executed by district authorities without interrupting policy implementation (Noda, 2019).

3.5. Adjusting the implementation of policies on training, retraining and civil servants

Implementing the policy of training and fostering Khmer civil servants in the Mekong Delta region in recent times has shown that the policy still has limitations and inadequacies that need to be more consistent with reality in localities (Ngo et al., 2019). This limitation and inadequacy are reflected in the selection of training and fostering majors for civil servants that must be consistent with fact, mainly with sufficient qualifications. Social management in areas with significant ethnic minorities with different characteristics must change content and training programs accordingly (Nor et al., 2022). In addition, many civil servants are sent for exercises that are not suitable for their titles. Therefore, in organizing training and retraining policies, Khmer civil servants at all levels of party committees and local authorities propose to the Departments of Home Affairs to submit to the provincial People's Committee to adjust policy implementation training and fostering. They were adjusting training programs and contents to suit the situation (Nguyen, 2022). From the adjustments of the agency in charge of policy implementation in the provinces of the Mekong Delta, the party committees and local authorities of the districts will adjust the above policy implementation solutions according to the province's plan, adjusting the implementation of the policy (Phuong et al., 2022). Select necessary majors and qualifications to train and foster different subjects; Support funding for training and retraining to ensure benefits for civil servants after training and retraining to improve capacity when returning to work in the locality. The issue of building a team of ethnic minority civil servants on the spot is a topic of concern to the state (Pribadi & Kim, 2022). However, some places implementing this policy still need to be more flexible in proposing appropriate solutions, leading to the policy's goals not achieving the desired results.

Through preliminary and final reports on implementing training and retraining policies for Khmer civil servants, the district People's Committee proposed and recommended adjustments to some of the training and retraining policies for civil servants to suit the local situation (Quang, 2022). Accordingly, the adjustment is made toward increasing support allowances for civil servants participating in training and refresher courses, expanding the number of subjects assigned for training (Reddick et al., 2022). However, the level of adjustment and suitability of the policy is not much and has yet to keep up with the actual situation.

To evaluate adjustments in implementing training and retraining policies for Khmer civil servants in the Mekong Delta. The authors surveyed the opinions of relevant civil servants on three contents, including the policy content: Is the adjustment consistent with the reality and policies of the central and provincial governments? Results of policy implementation are updated and synthesized as a basis for policy adjustment. The procedure is adjusted but ensures its durability and stability, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Assessment of Khmer civil servants on adjustments in implementing training and fostering policies for civil servants

Source: Summary of survey data processing results, September 2023

3.6. Monitor, inspect and urge the implementation of training and fostering policies for civil servants

In implementing the policy on training and fostering Khmer civil servants, the Department of Home Affairs has presided over developing a plan to monitor, inspect and supervise the implementation of the policy on training and fostering Khmer civil servants in the Mekong Delta. On that basis, the Department of Home Affairs in the provinces established an inspection team including the Provincial People's Committee, the Department of Home Affairs and relevant departments, divisions and branches to inspect the implementation of training and retraining policies for civil servants Khmer. The inspection content focuses on planning, reviewing the standards of staff and civil servants, monitoring activity and fostering,

dissemination and propaganda work, and maintaining policy implementation (Rey-Moreno et al., 2018). From the work of monitoring, inspecting and urging the implementation of training and fostering policies for Khmer civil servants, the provincial People's Committee, departments and branches have been interested in adjusting inadequacies in the implementation plan for training and enabling policies for civil servants (Sirgy et al., 2000).

Those inadequacies were discovered during monitoring, inspecting, and urging policy implementation and the agencies in charge of policy implementation in the province. Provincial People's Committee have adjusted and supplemented several policy implementation solutions to achieve the policy objectives and policy implementation plans set out by the area.

However, adjustment activities when implementing policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants that do not aim at policy goals are rectified as soon as problems are discovered. Adjusting solutions to enforce policies on training and cultivating Khmer civil servants has yet to bring about the effectiveness and efficiency of the policy. There are several reasons why civil servants reveal weaknesses in policy implementation and a low sense of responsibility in performing public duties, so inadequacies in training and retraining of civil servants, such as planning, have not been detected and sent to study (Song et al., 2017).

Training is organized at training facilities, and training textbooks and materials are inconsistent with local practice. The inadequacies in some localities have yet to be promptly resolved, so they have affected the effectiveness of implementing policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants. In some places, many complaints about land and corruption (Steppacher et al., 2021). Local civil servants' corruption affects the construction of new rural areas in the Mekong Delta region.

To evaluate the work of monitoring, inspecting and urging the implementation of training and fostering policies for Khmer civil servants, we surveyed Khmer civil servants, including the agency in charge of implementing training and promoting procedures (Suzuki & Demircioglu, 2021). Khmer civil servants check and inspect the contents of the policy implementation plan.

The agency in charge of implementing policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants has diverse and abundant forms of inspection and examination; The agency in charge of implementing procedures on training and promoting Khmer civil servants has a regular and continuous level of inspection and supervision; The survey results through consulting Khmer civil servants on these three contents are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Results of monitoring, inspecting and urging the implementation of training and fostering policies for civil servants

Source: Summary of survey data processing results, September 2023

3.7. Summarize and learn from experience in implementing training and fostering policies for civil servants

Summarizing and drawing experience from implementing training and retraining policies for Khmer civil servants is the final step in organizing and implementing training and retraining plans. Through summarizing, evaluating, and drawing experience, conclusions can be drawn about the direction and administration of the district People's Committee and the compliance of entities participating in implementing training and fostering policies. The government has carried out the assessment and summary thoughtfully and qualitatively (Tanny & Zafarullah, 2023).

The Conference summarized and learned from the implementation of socio-political tasks in localities while integrating it with the assessment of the performance of training and fostering policies shown in the Conference's critical summaries, including talks summarizing emulation and reward work and the Conference translating training and promoting employment (Tran & Dollery, 2023). In particular, civil servant conferences are held annually to reassess many aspects, including the capacity of civil servants to perform public duties associated with implementing training and fostering policies for civil servants above the district area (Wang & Ma, 2022). At these conferences, all related issues, including the content of training and

retraining and remuneration for civil servants participating in training and retraining, are evaluated by a large number of civil servants in order to recommend to the agency in charge of policy implementation. The problems and shortcomings in the local policy implementation process to develop practical solutions to implement the policy. However, the organization and evaluation of implementing policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants in some localities have yet to receive adequate attention. The review of policy implementation is still a formality to achieve achievements. There needs to be specific analysis and assessment to point out apparent shortcomings in the implementation process, especially in the participation of subjects sent for training and fostering in this policy, which is not by the planning.

To evaluate the work of summarizing and evaluating lessons learned in the process of implementing policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants, we surveyed Khmer civil servants in 3 contents, including Does the agency in charge of implementing training and retraining policies for Khmer civil servants regularly organize reviews and evaluations of policy implementation? Has the agency in charge of implementing the policy on training and fostering Khmer civil servants drawn on the results and limitations of the policy implementation process? The agency in charge of implementing the policy on training and cultivating Khmer civil servants has learned from experience in implementing the policy. The results of the opinion survey of Khmer civil servants on these three contents are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Evaluation of opinions of civil servants on summarizing and learning from the implementation of training and fostering policies for civil servants

Source: Summary of survey data processing results, September 2023

4. DISCUSSION

Planning is the first step in policy implementation steps and is also quite essential to help guide policy implementation activities. Poor planning will lead to many situations arising during policy implementation, requiring adjustment, supplementation, and completion. In planning policy implementation, the plan's goals should be clearly defined. Any content or activity must be directed towards a common goal; otherwise, it will go astray and not achieve the desired results. In implementing training and retraining policies, Khmer civil servants should determine which agency is the subject of policy implementation, avoid overlapping, shifting responsibilities, causing difficulties and limiting implementation effectiveness policy exam (Wirtz & Kurtz, 2016). The coordination mechanism between levels and agencies at the same level should be considered to create strictness in coordination, sharing and information disclosure.

Promoting the agency's role in proactively advising and developing training and retraining plans based on correctly identifying training and retraining needs is essential for designing content and programs associated with capacity, thereby choosing appropriate training and fostering forms and content (Yu, 2021). To do this, the district People's Committee must perform well in statistics, planning, and civil servant work, and at the same time, based on the capacity framework and job position, register training quotas correctly. Many localities have recently paid little attention to implementing this policy. Since then, the demand registration status has been based on targets, spontaneously and not by the district's plans and policies. Therefore, localities should focus on selecting subjects according to training and retraining requirements; Khmer civil servants should participate in training and retraining to ensure standards.

The development of training and retraining plans should be based on meeting the requirements of creating civil servants who are both rosy and professional with political ethics, sound expertise, a sense of responsibility, and dedication to serving. Implement the training and retraining plan approved by the Provincial People's Committee, contributing to creating a source of future civil servants and enhancing capacity building, management and administration capabilities, and professional expertise of district-level civil servants.

Ensure that the consideration of placement, appointment, promotion, and promotion of civil servants must be based on planning associated with training and fostering to ensure compliance with prescribed standards, and at the same time, need to consistently and strictly implement measures civil servants introduce. Implementing the process of electing critical positions at the district level accordingly, training and fostering plans are adhered to to proactively implement one step ahead to promptly meet requirements demand for standardization of work (Yuguo & Hindy, 2018). In reality, some party committees at all levels have yet to do an excellent job in planning and civil servants, which has led to the fact that some civil servants elected to hold critical positions lack standard diplomas and certificates.

Based on planning approved by competent authorities, develop training and retraining plans to meet work requirements synchronously carry out the stages of assessment, planning, training, arrangement, and use. Proactively conduct advanced training to supplement necessary skills and knowledge according to prescribed standards to create conditions for civil servants to access planning. Establish a strict and scientific planning sequence for building a coordinated training plan. Organize a summary and evaluation of implementation results to draw experiences to gradually complete the training and retraining plan for Khmer civil servants to serve well in the coming years.

Attach the responsibility of local leaders to training and retraining, and overcome the fear of having civil servants under your authority have higher qualifications than yourself. Civil servants sent to training and fostering overcome the ideology of placing importance on degrees to get promoted without striving to train political bravery, ethics, and working style while avoiding school. Encourage and create conditions for civil servants to self-study to improve their qualifications and professional expertise in many forms, such as centralized, semi-centralized, online, and remote; this contributes to reducing the burden on the state budget for training work.

The success of organizing and implementing policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants largely depends on the assignment and coordination of policy implementation. When assigning and coordinating scientific, strict and reasonable policy implementation, policy implementation will be highly effective. That is shown in the clear and specific assignment of powers and responsibilities to each relevant organization and individual participating in implementing policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants. Clearly define the role of each participant in policy implementation. Through assigning and coordinating the implementation of policies, we will be able to see the achievements and limitations of the participants, thereby discussing and agreeing on adjustments to organize and implement the policies (Zhang et al., 2022).

Develop coordination regulations to ensure consistency throughout the district in implementing policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants. With this regulation, it is possible to create a joint commitment, serving as a basis for adjusting coordination activities between training and retraining establishments and agencies related to training, retraining, and public policies Khmer position. This regulation will clearly define the responsibilities of each agency and locality in all stages of the policy implementation process and the agency in charge of implementing the policy on training and fostering Khmer civil servants.

5. CONCLUSION

Implementing policies to train and foster Khmer civil servants in the Mekong Delta region plays a vital role in helping improve the quality of civil servants at the district level, meeting the area's economic, social and cultural development requirements. Implementing the policy of training and fostering Khmer civil servants will help improve local civil servants' professional knowledge, skills, expertise and political ideology. This will help local civil servants meet job requirements and improve work efficiency. In particular, implementing the policy of training

and fostering Khmer civil servants will help ensure ethnic diversity among civil servants, strengthening national solidarity and creating sympathy and respect between people of the nation.

Implementing policies to train and foster Khmer civil servants will also create opportunities for ethnic minorities to participate in community activities, contribute to local development, and, at the same time, help improve quality of life and reduce development gaps between regions. Implementing policies to train and foster Khmer civil servants also helps promote cultural development, honouring the cultural values and customs of the Khmer and other ethnic groups in the Mekong Delta region.

Research and implement policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants according to a seven-step process, including: (1) developing a plan to implement the policy; (2) disseminate and propagate policy implementation contents; (3) assignment and coordination of policy implementation; (4) maintain policy implementation; (5) adjust policy implementation; (6) monitor, inspect, and urge policy implementation; (7) summarize, evaluate, and learn from policy implementation. Through analyzing the implementation of training and retraining policies for Khmer civil servants in the Mekong Delta, the topic focuses on researching the current status of the implementation process of training and retraining policies for Khmer civil servants in the Mekong Delta through seven steps.

Based on the current status of steps to implement policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants in the Mekong Delta region. We make assessments by ensuring requirements in the organization of policy implementation, subjects participating in the performance and pointing out advantages, achieved results, limitations and inadequacies in the policy implementation process. Issues have been raised in implementing policies on training and fostering Khmer civil servants in the Mekong Delta region in the coming period to meet the cause of regional development to implement national and national target programs in the country in the context of increasingly deep international integration.

Disclosure Statement: The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

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